

Studies on the Interaction of Sodium Pentacyano-Ammine Ferrate(II) with Pyridine, Quinoline and N-Dimethylaniline

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Sodium pentacyano-amine-ferrate (II) reacts slowly in about 4 hr with pyridine, quinoline and N-dimethylaniline to give green colored complexes, which have been isolated as their zinc salts. Increase in pH during the reaction and chemical analysis of the zinc salts show that the base molecule enters the coordination sphere of iron by displacing ammonia. The coordination of the base to iron is supported by infrared spectra of the complexes. Magnetic measurements show the complexes to be diamagnetic as expected for low spin complexes of iron(II).

ORGANIC bases¹ react with potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) without entering the coordination sphere of iron to give addition products², where the protonated base replaces the cations of the hexacyanoferrate(II) complex. In contrast to this, in the reactions of such bases with pentacyano-amine-ferrate(II), the ammine group was found to be substituted³ by the organic base to give coloured soluble complexes. Due to the rapid development of colour these reactions have been recommended^{4,5} for spot test analysis of azide, thiocyanate and organic functional groups like aromatic amines, aromatic aldehydes, thiolaldehydes, hydrazinos etc. Herrington has also used pentacyano-amine-ferrate(II) as an analytical reagent for the estimation of some bases⁶. In view of the importance of these reactions in spot test analysis and analytical applications, studies have been carried out on the interaction of pentacyano-amine-ferrate(II) with tertiary bases: pyridine, quinoline and N-dimethylaniline.

Experimental

Solutions of the organic bases were prepared in double distilled water (all glass) using a minimum quantity of ethanol to obtain clear solutions.

pH measurements were carried out on a Cambridge bench type pH meter using glass electrodes. Spectrophotometric studies were carried out with Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer. Infra red spectra were recorded on Beckmann IR 20 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. Magnetic measurements were carried out by Gouy's method at room temperature ($30 \pm 1^\circ$).

$\text{Na}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{NH}_3]$ was prepared from sodium nitroprusside and its solution was prepared in conductivity water and standardised potentiometrically⁷ against KMnO_4 .

All attempts to isolate the complexes in the acid form $\text{H}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{R}]$, where R is the organic base, or as the trisodium salt were unsuccessful. The complexes were, therefore, isolated as the zinc salts. To a solution of zinc acetate (4 g) in dilute acetic acid (20 ml of glacial acid and 100 ml of water) was added to the green coloured solution of the complex. A gelatinous precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed with water (till free from acid), alcohol, then ether and dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Nitrogen and carbon in the complexes were estimated at microanalytical laboratories, Panjab University, Chandigarh (India). For metal estimation, the complexes were digested with concentrated hydrochloric acid and iron and zinc were estimated⁸ gravimetrically as $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and ZnNH_4PO_4 respectively. Water was estimated by desiccating the complex in an oven at 110° for 3-4 hr.

Results and Discussion

Mixtures of pentacyano-amine-ferrate(II) and pyridine, quinoline and N-dimethylaniline give green coloured solutions on standing for about 4 hr. The pH of 0.02M pyridine solution was 7.62 while that of $\text{Na}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{NH}_3]$ of the same concentration was 9.40. After mixing equal volumes of the two solutions, the initial pH was 8.24 which rose to 10.10 on keeping for 4 hr. Similar increase in pH was observed with the other two bases and was found to be 10.36 and 9.50 after 4 hr. with N-dimethylaniline and quinoline respectively. The increase in pH may be attributed to the release of NH_3 on substitution by the base, according to the following equation:

Spectrophotometric studies show that the green coloured solutions show new regions of absorption at 660 nm for N-dimethylaniline, 640 nm for quinoline

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and 650 nm for pyridine, whereas both pentacyanoammine-ferrate(II) and the base show negligible absorption in that region. Continuous variation and molar ratio methods show the formation of 1:1 complexes which is supported by chemical analysis data (Table 1). The stability constant of the complexes could be calculated using the spectrophotometric data: $\log K = 4.47, 4.38$ and 4.43 ; $\Delta G^\circ = -6.10, -5.90$ and -6.04 Kcal/mole for the pyridine, quinoline and N-dimethylaniline complexes respectively. The isolated complexes may thus be assigned the general formula: $Zn_3[Fe(CN)_5R]_2 \cdot yH_2O$, where R is pyridine, quinoline or N-dimethylaniline.

The infrared spectral characteristics (Table 2) show that the base is present in the coordination sphere of iron. A broad band at 3300 cm^{-1} and 1620 cm^{-1} in all the complexes may be assigned to water of crystallisation. The band at 3300 cm^{-1} cannot be assigned to NH_3 since the usual $\delta_s(NH_3)$ band around 1300 cm^{-1} is missing in the spectra of the new complex. The typical $C \equiv N$ stretching appears at 2060 cm^{-1} in all the complexes. Binding of the

base with iron is borne out by the following assignments: In the case of pyridine four bands appearing in the $1600\text{--}1430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region are shifted to higher frequencies^{9,10} on complexation as listed below:

Pyridine	1600	1570	1490	1440
Complex with pyridine.	1615	1575	1495	1445

The C-H in-plane deformation and breathing vibrations at $1375\text{ cm}^{-1}, 1070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1035 in pyridine are observed at higher frequencies in the complex with pyridine. This shows that pyridine is coordinated to iron. The structure of quinoline is similar to pyridine and hence the same considerations hold good in that case also. In the case of N-dimethylaniline the C-N stretching appearing at 1345 and 1180 cm^{-1} shifts to 1390 cm^{-1} and 1165 cm^{-1} in the complex showing coordination to iron.

Magnetic measurements show the complexes to be diamagnetic indicating low-spin character of these iron(II) complexes.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Chemical analysis					
	Zn	Fe	N	C	H ₂ O	
$Zn_3[Fe(CN)_5(C_5H_5N)]_2 \cdot 3H_2O$	25.22	14.49	21.73	31.05	4.46	% Calcd.
	25.45	14.81	21.87	31.25	4.40	% Found
$Zn_3[Fe(CN)_5(C_8H_{11}N)]_2 \cdot 3H_2O$	22.39	12.86	19.28	35.82	6.12	% Calcd.
	22.91	13.05	19.64	35.67	6.45	% Found
$Zn_3[Fe(CN)_5(C_8H_7N)]_2 \cdot H_2O$	23.13	13.29	19.93	39.86	2.14	% Calcd.
	23.47	13.09	19.74	39.54	2.00	% Found

TABLE 2. IMPORTANT INFRARED SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Absorption band at (cm^{-1})													
	$\nu(H_2O)$	$\nu(NH_3)$	$\nu(C \equiv N)$	H ₂ O	ring stretching vibrations				$\delta_s(NH_3)$	C-H in-plane vibrations			Fe-C	Fe-N
Pentacyanoammine-ferrate(II)	3400	3280	2020	1620	—	—	—	—	1260	—	—	—	560	490
pyridine	—	—	—	—	1600	1570	1490	1440	—	1375	1070	1035	—	—
pyridine complex	3340	—	2060	1620	1615	1575	1495	1445	—	1380	1100	1060	570	440
quinoline	—	—	—	—	1590	1565	1495	1430	—	1370	1090	1030	—	—
quinoline complex	3340	—	2060	1620	1600	1580	1500	1450	—	1390	1110	1060	575	450
					$\nu(C-N)$									
N-dimethylaniline	—	—	—	—	1345		1190		—	—	—	—	—	—
N-dimethylaniline complex	3300	—	2060	1620	1390		1165		—	—	—	—	580	450

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